

Breast absorbed dose in women undergoing chest radiographs

Hendriil Humberto da Silveira Urzêdo
 Programa de Pós Graduação em Engenharia
 Biomédica
 Universidade Federal de Uberlândia
 Uberlândia, Brazil
 ORCID: 0000-0002-4953-7525

Ana Claudia Patrocinio
 Programa de Pós Graduação em Engenharia
 Biomédica
 Universidade Federal de Uberlândia
 Uberlândia, Brazil
 ORCID: 0000-0001-9376-7689

Abstract—Chest radiographs are among the most commonly performed in emergency units, raising concern about the radiation dose this region receives. Estimating the dose absorbed by the breast is important in this type of exam, since the biological risk caused by ionizing radiation when crossing and interacting with tissues and cells may trigger several abnormalities, including cancer, such as breast cancer. The objective of this work is to simulate the dose that the breast receives in this type of exam. For this, data were collected from women who underwent chest radiography in two emergency units in Uberlândia - MG and processed by the CALDose_X 5.0 program. The mean absorbed dose in unit A patients was 0.037 mGy while in unit B it was 0.019 mGy. The parameters used in this study compared to others were similar. There are divergences in standard chest X-ray examinations and therefore directly affect the radiation dose the patient receives.

Keywords—chest radiography, absorbed dose, breast

I. INTRODUCTION

Radiological examinations are among the most requested in emergency units due to their importance to medical diagnosis [1], and radiography is the most widely used and accessible modality. Within this, the chest examination stands out as the most performed, most often by female patients with clinical symptoms of cardiorespiratory disease [2].

The increasingly common and recurrent use of this diagnostic feature exponentially increases the radiation dose absorbed by patients due to the exacerbated number of tests required. In contrast, the concern to reduce the dose absorbed by the patient in each exam has become the great paradigm of radiology [3]. It is important, according to Ministerial Ordinance 453/98 of the Ministry of Health, to know the dose received by the patient in order to optimize exposure avoiding unnecessary excesses to him [4].

This concern is due to the biological risk caused by ionizing radiation when passing through and interacting with tissues and cells that can trigger several abnormalities, including cancer, such as breast cancer. The risk of cancer incidence depends, in the case of radioinduction, on the absorbed dose in the organ, the type of irradiated organ, age and gender of the exposed individuals, despite being multifactorial [5,6].

Breast cancer is the most common type of cancer among women and is the second most common cancer in the world with the projection for the 2018-2019 biennium about 59,700 new cases in Brazil, with an estimated risk of 56.33 cases per 100 one thousand women [7]. It represents 25% of all

cancers worldwide, being the fifth leading cause of death in the world and the leading cause of cancer death in Brazil. Incidence rates vary by region, with highest rates in the most affluent regions: from 27 per 100,000 individuals in East Africa and East Asia to 96 per 100,000 individuals in Western Europe and increasing each year [8].

Estimating the risk of organ and tissue cancer is complicated because it requires direct determination of organ and tissue doses, which is often impossible to perform. An alternative to solve the problem is to use computer simulation to estimate organ and tissue doses [5].

The objective of this study is to evaluate the dose received by a patient on chest X-ray, based on routine data collected from a Emergency Care Unit service and to estimate, by simulation, the dose received on the breast in these exams.

II. METHODOLOGY

For this study, data were collected from 33 patients from two public units of Emergency Care in the city of Uberlândia-MG, 20 from a unit named A and 13 from the second named B. The patients selected for data collection were female, between 20 and 80 years old, who underwent posteroanterior (PA) chest radiography. In these incidences, the distance between the X-ray source and the image receiver (SID) was one meter and eighty centimeters (1.80 m) in an orthostatic position, made on the stand of the device.

At each exposure, the acquisition parameters were selected and the following data were collected: voltage (kV), product current time (mAs) and current (mA), as well as SID and age. In unit A the current used was 320 mA, the current varied between 70 and 90 kV and the current product time between 8 and 12.5 mAs. In unit B the selected current was 200 mA, the lowest voltage was 62 kV and the highest was 70 kV and two values of current product time were selected, 10 and 13.3 mAs.

The X-ray machine in unit A is SIEMENS Polymat Plus S, model No. 7037182, series No. 1379, produced in Germany and manufactured in the year 2007. In unit B, in turn, has the device of tecnodesing TD500. Both devices are analog using the screen / film system with automatic darkroom film development.

Data were obtained according to the demand for examinations in two emergency units from July to August 2019.

After collection, the data were processed using the CALDose_X 5.0 program, a software tool that provides the

ability to calculate incident air kerma (INAK) and input surface air kerma (ESAK), two important data used in x-ray examinations. In addition, the software uses conversion coefficients (CCs) to evaluate the absorbed dose in organs and tissues of the human body, the effective dose and the risk of cancer for radiographic examinations. In the CALDose_X 5.0 system, CCs, ratios of absorbed doses of organs or tissues, and measurable quantities were calculated with the FAX06 and MAX06 phantoms for 34 projections of 10 commonly performed x-ray examinations for 40 combinations of varying tube current and filtration ranging from 50 to 120 kVp and 2.0 to 5.0 mm aluminum, respectively, for various field positions, for 29 selected organs and tissues, and simultaneously for measurable quantities, INAK, ESAK and kerma area product (KAP). Based on user-defined X-ray irradiation parameters, CALDose_X shows phantom images along with the position of the x-ray beam [9].

In this work, the doses were simulated with the data related to the acquisition of the acquisition data of the collected exams. For the use of the system, the patient's age must be informed (no name, institution or medical record required, although there is an option), the sex and the position of the exam, in this case, orthostatic, the type of exam must be chest, and the posterior-anterior projection (PA). In item "X-RAY PIPE" focus-detector distance (FDD), Load (mAs) and voltage (kV) must be entered. In this work, the FDD was fixed at 180 cm. Subsequent to the default field position was selected and then calculated to INAK (incident air kerma). A new tab opens informing you that the theoretical yield will be used, being necessary to show the selected curve and apply it. You must then calculate INAK in order to calculate the absorbed dose by choosing INAK as the normalization quantity. This provides all organ and tissue absorbed dose data in milliGray (mGy).

III. RESULTS

The results are shown in Tables 1 and 2, referring to units A and B respectively, whose patients were listed according to the collection site, from 1A to 20A for unit A and 1B to 13B for unit B in increasing order of age and the technical factors voltage and current product time of each exam, followed by the simulated dose in the CALDose_X 5.0 program.

TABLE I. BREAST ABSORBED DOSE ON CHEST X-RAY OF UNIT A PATIENT

Patient	Age	Voltage (kV)	Current product time (mAs)	Breast dose (mGy)
1A	27	81	10.0	0.033
2A	31	81	10.0	0.033
3A	32	85	10.0	0.038
4A	37	81	10.0	0.033
5A	37	85	12.5	0.048
6A	40	81	10.0	0.033
7A	41	77	10.0	0.028
8A	45	85	12.5	0.048
9A	46	85	10.0	0.038
10A	47	77	10.0	0.028

Patient	Age	Voltage (kV)	Current product time (mAs)	Breast dose (mGy)
11A	47	85	12.5	0.048
12A	48	81	10.0	0.033
13A	49	77	10.0	0.028
14A	49	81	12.5	0.041
15A	51	85	12.5	0.048
16A	58	81	10.0	0.033
17A	62	85	10.0	0.038
18A	64	90	12.5	0.058
19A	67	81	12.5	0.041
20A	70	70	8.0	0.016
<i>Avarege</i>	<i>47.4</i>	<i>81.7</i>	<i>10.7</i>	<i>0.037</i>

TABLE II. BREAST ABSORBED DOSE ON CHEST X-RAY OF UNIT B PATIENT

Patient	Age	Voltage (kV)	Current product time (mAs)	Breast dose (mGy)
1B	28	63	13.3	0.017
2B	41	61	13.3	0.015
3B	42	63	13.3	0.017
4B	42	64	13.3	0.018
5B	48	62	13.3	0.016
6B	49	65	13.3	0.019
7B	50	68	13.3	0.023
8B	54	65	13.3	0.019
9B	58	73	10.0	0.023
10B	58	70	13.3	0.026
11B	61	64	13.3	0.018
12B	72	68	10.0	0.017
13B	76	64	13.3	0.018
<i>Avarege</i>	<i>52.2</i>	<i>64.5</i>	<i>12.8</i>	<i>0,037</i>

IV. DISCUSSION

Using software such as CALDose_X 5.0 is an efficient method to estimate the absorbed dose in organs through the use of computational phantoms, allowing the study time to be optimized by the speed of calculations performed by the program. This is confirmed by comparative studies between physical phantoms and mathematical models, in which the latter present similarities of results with the former [10].

There is a significant difference in the average current used in both units, being A (81.7 kV) higher than B (65.4 kV), while average current product time at B (12.8 mAs) is slightly higher. greater than in A (10.7 mAs). As a result the average absorbed dose in unit A patients (0.037 mGy) is almost double the average of unit B (0.019 mGy). The mean age, in turn, was higher in unit B (52.2 years) than in A (47.4

years). When comparing the Ofori study, which used the same dose simulation program to calculate the skin entry dose and the effective dose in various body regions, including the chest, ages ranged for chest PA between 25 and 73 years with an average of 43 years, current ranged from 65 to 90 kV with an average of 80.5 kV, current product time ranged from 12.5 to 30 mAs, average 25.5 mAs and the SID averaged 105.5 cm (ranging from 90 to 110 cm) [11].

Aliasgharzadeh in turn collected data (current, current product time and SID) from chest radiographs in PA at different hospitals in Iran to calculate the effective dose that the chest receives in these examinations and reported that the main reason for overdose is lower current values and higher current product time values (this can be observed when comparing the technical factors and the absorbed dose of patients 20A and 10B), apart from that, newer equipment and higher SID may be linked to the lower dose to the patient [12].

These variations are common and may be related to the characteristics of the institutions such as the device, the technician performing the examination and the process of chemical development of the radiographic film, as well as the anatomical variations of the patients. One way to standardize exam execution and all processes involved is the implementation of Quality Control Programs (QCP) in radiology departments to reduce disparity in different units [13].

Despite the variation in dose by the mother in the different units studied, when compared to other types of tests that use X-rays is much smaller. An example is the study by Lahham, in which the dose the breast receives on chest tomographic examination is 15 mGy on average, much higher than the average PA chest radiographs obtained from this study [14].

V. CONCLUSION

There are divergences in standard chest X-ray examinations and therefore directly affect the radiation dose the patient receives. The implementation of quality control programs and the optimization of technical factors help to reduce this dose, being necessary, considering the important role of this exam and the high percentage of medical requests for its performance.

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